

Organometallic Compounds of Copper(II) derived from some Dicarboxylic Acids

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Metal-bound formate (M-O₂CH) and hydroxycarbonyl (M-CO₂H) often form metal hydride species with elimination of carbon dioxide¹. Also, CO₂ gas is liberated on heating phthalic acid salt with mercury or its complexes with copper(II) and nickel(II), yielding organometallic compounds. Similar products can also be expected on heating the metal complexes of other carboxylic acids. Thus, the present work reports the synthesis of organometallic compounds derived from three dicarboxylic (succinic, tartaric and adipic) acids.

Results and Discussion

The complexes have general formula CuL.4H₂O, where L = succinic, tartaric or adipic acid. The copper-succinic acid complex decomposes on heating in absence of air, followed by colour changes from greenish blue to light bluish green, light brown and brown at temperatures ~120, ~270 and ~300° respectively. Displacement in molecules is observed at ~120°, which may be expected due to decomposition and vapourisation of coordinated water molecules (Scheme 1). On further heating, probably two CO₂ molecules are almost simultaneously eliminated. Thus, only the final product C₂H₄Cu could be prepared in pure state by heating the complex at 300° for ~1 h.

The decomposition of the copper-tartaric acid complex also shows three colour changes, i.e., white-blue, brown and dark brown. It may be due to close structural similarity in the complexes of succinic acid and tartaric acid. Elimination of coordinated water molecules may be expected by colour change and displacement of molecules at ~130°. The final product is CuC₂H₄O₂ (dark brown).

Displacement in molecules as a result of heating the copper adipate complex occurs at 250°, followed by reduction in colour intensity of the complex. Unlike succinic acid and tartaric acid systems, only two colour changes are observed. The second colour change appears at 280° due to elimination of one CO₂ molecule. A black mass obtained at 290° does not correspond to expected five-membered cyclic structure (C₄H₈Cu). The brown product prepared by heating the complex at 280° for ~2 h turns greyish brown, on cooling and keeping in air, by absorbing water from atmosphere.

Liberation of four coordinated water molecules in the temperature range 110–150, 100–135 and 120–250° from copper carboxylate complexes with succinic, tartaric and

Scheme 1

adipic acids respectively, is also indicated by heating these complexes in air (TGA analysis). But, beyond temperature 210, 175 and 270°, decomposition of the resulting dehydrated products C₄H₄O₄Cu, C₄H₄O₆Cu and C₆H₈O₄Cu occurs, yielding metal oxide at 400, 340, 400° respectively.

The three cyclic copper compounds isolated through thermal decomposition of the corresponding Cu-dicarboxylic acid complexes are soluble in methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO and insoluble in water and dilute H₂SO₄ solution. The compounds (Table 1) were characterised by elemental analyses, decomposition temperature and infrared spectra. The structure of C₂H₄O₂Cu was further supported by its molecular weight obtained by mass spectra.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Yield (%) (Decomp. temp., °C)	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
		C	H	Cu
C ₂ H ₄ Cu	98.0 (315)	26.18 (26.21)	4.38 4.37	89.56 89.41)
C ₂ H ₄ O ₂ Cu	96.5 (340)	19.46 (19.42)	3.24 3.24	51.25 51.43)
C ₅ H ₈ O ₂ Cu.2H ₂ O	97.0 (295) ^a	30.16 (30.06)	4.01 4.00	31.75 31.84)

^aDehydrated species (C₅H₈O₂Cu).

Ir spectra of all the compounds exhibit strong bands at 2850, 1420 and 1360 cm^{-1} due to C-H stretching, scissoring and skeletal vibration of the molecules respectively. The bands at 705, 685 and 695 cm^{-1} , respectively of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cu}$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{Cu}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, are assigned to the $\nu_{\text{Cu}-\text{C}}$ vibration. The bands at lower frequency in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{Cu}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be due to the presence of oxygen atom with organic residue which reduces Cu-C bond order. A weak and broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ is assigned to ν_{OH} vibration. In $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{Cu}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the presence of coordinated water molecule is supported by the appearance of a medium but broad band at 3420 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} mode, followed by medium intensity bands at 940 and 805 cm^{-1} being assigned to the rocking and wagging vibrations of water molecule. A weak and broad band at 640 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\nu_{\text{Cu}-\text{O}}$ stretching vibration³ of the coordinated water. Bonding of metal through oxygen of organic residue is confirmed by the medium intensity band at 520 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ mode of vibration is indicated by the weak but sharp band at 1620 cm^{-1} . Deviation of vibration towards lower frequency from the normal absorption position may be correlated with the influence of electronic effects $(-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\overset{\ominus}{\text{O}}-\longleftrightarrow-\overset{\ominus}{\text{O}}-\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}=\text{O}-)$ which arises from the lone-pair of electrons on oxygen.

Cyclic structures of the organometallic compounds are also favoured by their high decomposition temperature (Table 1). The mass spectrum of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ (m/z 124) also confirms its proposed structure, and hence the structure of other two compounds, specially $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cu}$, as all have close structural similarities on the basis of their route of synthesis, group vibration in the infrared region and high decomposition temperature.

Experimental

All the chemicals (B.D.H./Glaxo) were used as such.

Copper carboxylate complexes : An aqueous solution of copper nitrate (6.14 g in 100 cm^3) was added (dropwise) to a solution of sodium succinate (a mixture of 3.0 g succinic acid and 2.03 g sodium hydroxide in 100 cm^3 distilled water). The separated greenish blue solid was washed

with water and dried at room temperature under reduced pressure. Similarly copper complexes of tartaric and adipic acids were prepared.

Conversion of copper-carboxylate into cyclic compounds : The copper-carboxylate (1 : 1) complexes with succinic, tartaric and adipic acids were heated separately at 300, 315 and 280° respectively, in absence of air. After 1 h heating, the succinic acid and tartaric acid complexes yielded brown coloured organometallic cyclic compounds $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cu}$ and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$ respectively. Decomposition of adipic acid complex was complete in ~2 h yielding the greyish brown cyclic product $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{Cu}$. This product on cooling and keeping in air absorbed two water molecules from atmosphere.

C and H were analysed at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Cu was determined complexometrically with EDTA⁴ after decomposing the complex with fusion mixture, concentrated H_2SO_4 and a pinch of urea. FAB mass spectrum was recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-60 spectrometer using argon/xenon (6 kV, 100 mA) as FAB gas and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer.

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